

Mitigating User Misconduct and Enhancing Resource Security of University Libraries in Bayelsa State

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Abstract

Purpose: The researchers conducted a comprehensive examination of the various user misconduct prevention measures implemented by libraries and assessed the overall security of the library's resources at Bayelsa State University.

Methodology: The study was guided by three research questions and three hypotheses. This study adopted a correlational research design. The population of this research comprised 83 library staff members of the Bayelsa State University libraries, who were also used as the sample, hence adopting a census sampling technique. The data collection instrument was a researcher-developed questionnaire rated on a 4-point Likert scale. The data collected from the respondents were properly organised in tables, coded, and analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.0, while Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to test the hypotheses.

Findings: The study finds a significant, moderate, positive relationship between user education and the security of library resources in Bayelsa State universities. Additionally, a strong positive relationship exists between the presence of security personnel at the library entrance and the security of library resources. Furthermore, signage displaying library rules and regulations shows a significant, moderate positive relationship with library security resources.

Conclusion/Recommendation: The researchers recommend that institutions allocate additional resources to strengthen user education programs, such as deploying skilled security professionals at library entrances and other high-traffic areas. They also recommend using simple, clear language and infographics to improve the visibility of rules and regulations.

Keywords: University Library, User Misconduct, Security, Prevention, Library Resources

Introduction

The primary purpose of any university library is to provide the information resources that enhance user satisfaction with their information needs and support the university's teaching, learning, and research goals (Mmejim & Umahi, 2019). To achieve this, the library aligns all its services toward this objective. A key responsibility of the university library is to ensure that all required resources are current and reliable, fulfilling its service role and meeting the expectations of the university community. The library offers services that meet users' information, educational, and recreational needs, either directly through direct contact with patrons or indirectly through behind-the-scenes activities. It is essential for the library to acquire and maintain a collection of information resources valued by users, including traditional materials such as books, journals, periodicals, theses, and dissertations, as well as realia,

visual materials, audio materials, e-resources, and databases. Additionally, internet connectivity is vital for providing users with easy access to timely, up-to-date information.

To ensure effective service delivery to its clients, the university library must properly manage and secure its resources. One might then ask, what resources does the library have at its disposal for efficient use? A resource is anything an individual or organisation needs to operate effectively. There are three main types of resources vital for any project and essential for project managers to plan carefully: human resources (personnel), financial resources (costs), and material goods (information resources). Libraries' information resources face various security threats from both humans and the natural environment. A key threat is user misconduct, which involves violating rules or committing offences. Egbuchu (2016) defines misconduct as acts that breach rules and regulations. Such misconduct can range from inappropriate user behaviour to attacks on library resources, facilities, equipment, and even staff. Given the diverse backgrounds of library patrons, the facility is vulnerable to numerous security risks and misconduct stemming from user actions.

Libraries actively try to manage users' behaviour. Harris, as cited in Edom (2012), notes that libraries provide a consistent study environment but face challenges, including user misconduct in university libraries. Negative attitudes among some users often hinder the quality of service. Here, 'users' are individuals seeking information resources to fulfil their needs. These users come from diverse backgrounds—familial, economic, social, cultural, and educational—and utilise the library to access various types of information. Such misconduct damages the reputation of university libraries and adversely affects their services and resources.

Libraries have rules and regulations that guide their use. There is a need to make users aware of them. According to Egbuchu (2016), a major means of ensuring that users are aware of the library's rules and regulations is through a well-organised and administered library orientation and instruction program, often referred to as user education. It should not be surprising that most library users are unaware of the rules and regulations governing library use and of the implications of certain forms of misconduct. There should therefore be a frequent, well-designed approach to library user education programs to acquaint users with the library's rules and regulations. This will curtail some of the tendencies toward misconduct among users. Security awareness is one way to safeguard library information resources. Aguolu and Aguolu (2002) proposed that one feasible way to ensure the effective security of library materials is to increase security alertness, employ uniformed security guards, and engage library assistants as surveillance attendants. Porters should be present at their duty posts to check patrons in and out, and they should check patrons' bags if they are leaving with library materials. This is a welcome idea for the security of library resources. Well-trained security personnel stationed at the library entrance and exit doors to assist porters in their security efforts are ideal for detecting deviant activities by patrons, such as theft, in the library.

This study investigates the relationship between user misconduct prevention measures and the security of library resources at State University Libraries in Bayelsa State. It specifically focuses on Bayelsa State University libraries: Niger Delta University Library, Bayelsa Medical University Library, and University of Africa Library.

Statement of the Problem

The significance of resources to any venture or organisation is immense and cannot be overstated. The success or failure of a university library largely hinges on the availability and effectiveness of its resources. Therefore, library administrators must diligently safeguard these resources to preserve their value, accessibility, and contribution toward achieving the library's goals and meeting the expectations

of users and the university community. To achieve this, university libraries have frequently implemented measures to address the negative impact of users' misconduct on their resources.

Libraries consistently implement measures such as user education, electronic security devices, designated security staff, secure fixtures, and clear signage of rules to prevent predictable losses and misdemeanours on valuable collections, furniture, and equipment.

Despite librarians' efforts to secure library resources, particularly in academic libraries, incidents of user misconduct persist. These include lost materials, assaults on staff, mutilation of books, noise disturbances by students, and more. If such issues persist, the library will continue to lose resources, which could undermine its purpose and value. The key question is: why do users persist in misconduct? Is it related to the preventive measures in place? This study aims to identify the prevention strategies employed by the libraries of Bayelsa State University and to examine their effectiveness in protecting library resources.

Objectives

This study primarily aimed to examine the relationship between users' misdemeanour prevention measures and the security of library resources at the Bayelsa State University Libraries. Specifically, it intended to:

1. Investigate the relationship between user education and the security of the library's resources in Bayelsa State universities.
2. Determine the relationship between the provision of security personnel at the entrance of the library and the security of the library's resources in Bayelsa State universities.
3. Ascertain the relationship between signage display of library rules and regulations and the security of the library's resources in the Bayelsa State universities.

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated for this study:

H0₁: There is no significant relationship between user education and the security of the library's resources in Bayelsa State universities.

H0₂: There is no significant relationship between the provision of security personnel at the entrance of the library and the security of the library's resources in Bayelsa State universities.

H0₃: There is no significant relationship between the display of library rules and regulations and the security of the library's resources in Bayelsa State universities.

Literature Review

The quest for information as a resource has progressively broadened the categories of users of the library's information resources to include government officials, politicians, and diplomats who need information for decision-making. Library users may also be male or female, young or old, with unique family, cultural, social, economic, or educational backgrounds that, in one way or another, affect their behavioural patterns. Manson, cited in Okorie and Njoku (2016), proposed that users in the university library are categorised based on their diverse needs, including undergraduates, mature students, visiting faculty members, physically challenged students, motor-impaired students, and other members of the university community. In any ethical organisation, rules and regulations are established to guide activities and help achieve specific goals effectively. These rules are applicable to all types of libraries and environments. Their purpose is to regulate user behaviour, as described by Egbuchu (2016), who notes that library rules serve as guidelines to ensure patrons behave appropriately and enable the library to fulfil its purpose. These rules address the use of library materials and facilities, prohibit unruly conduct and inappropriate activities, and specify consequences for violations. Access to the library

depends on following these rules; ignorance of them is not an excuse for non-compliance. Egbuchu (2016) emphasises that rules should be clear and aligned with the library's objectives. Violating these rules constitutes misconduct or delinquency and may result in penalties imposed by library authorities.

Users' misdemeanours tarnish the university library's reputation, affecting its services and resources. Okogwu and Nnam (2013) define misdemeanour as an act or omission that violates the rules, regulations, or core values that guide a specific establishment. They further describe library misdemeanours as the use of illegitimate means to access library materials. Adenike and Raliat (2020) relate library misdemeanours to the abuse of materials, such as mutilation, theft, and other misconduct, which threaten the library and its staff. They also note that abuse can take various forms, including physical or verbal mistreatment of resources. Adekunle, Adekunjo, and Unuabor (2018) identify causes such as economic depression and insufficient user orientation as contributing to theft and vandalism of library materials.

Preventing users' misbehaviour in libraries is essential. Prevention involves stopping certain actions before they happen or preventing individuals from engaging in problematic behaviour. In the context of libraries, misbehaviour prevention encompasses strategies to reduce the frequency of such incidents. According to Ajegbomogun, as cited in Oyedum, Sanni, and Udoakang (2014), collection security is a process designed to protect library materials from improper handling or loss, covering both damage and theft or intrusion. Egbuchu (2016) explains that library security mainly involves safeguarding the physical safety of users, staff, and the collection. Researchers such as Mmejim and Umahi (2019), Edom (2012), and Egbuchu (2016) list various measures that can be implemented to minimise damage to collections and facilities and to reduce the occurrence of misconduct within the library.

The sustained orientation program, or user education, is an effective method that involves clearly communicating safety and security policies to library users and staff. Egbuchu (2016) highlights that a well-organised and managed orientation and instruction program—often referred to as user education—is crucial for ensuring that users understand the library's rules and regulations. Many users remain unaware of these rules, and failure to comply can result in penalties. The main goal of orientation programs is to familiarise users with the library's layout, inform them about available services, and educate them about the resources. Proper orientation helps users understand the established rules and the consequences of misconduct. Regular updates and reforms of these programs are essential. Ufuoma and Urhefe (2019) found that ignorance of rules, often due to a lack of awareness of security personnel at the entrance, is a chief cause of deviant behaviour among library users.

Using signage to display rules, regulations, and punishments is highly recommended in libraries. Awareness of consequences for each offence helps prevent potential misconduct by library users.

Method

This study adopted a correlational research design. The population of this study comprised 83 library staff members at the Bayelsa State University libraries, who were also used as the sample. Hence, a census sampling technique was adopted. The data collection instrument was a researcher-developed questionnaire rated on a four-point Likert scale. The data collected from the respondents were properly organised into tables, coded, and analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.0, while Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (PPMC) was used to test the hypotheses.

Data Analyses and Presentation

Table 1: Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Analysis of the relationship between user education and security of the library's resources in Bayelsa State universities

		Correlations		Decision
		User Education	Security	
User Education	Pearson Correlation	1	.43	Rejected
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	
	N	78	78	
Security	Pearson Correlation	.43	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		
	N	78	78	

*S= Significant $p < 0.05$

Legends:

n: Number of respondents r-squared: Coefficient of determination

In the statistical analysis of research question one, a moderate positive relationship was found between user education and the security of library resources in Bayelsa State universities, with a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.43$ (43.0%). Furthermore, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant relationship between user education and the security of library resources in Bayelsa State universities, was rejected, and the alternative hypothesis was upheld [$P = .000$ $p < 0.05$]. Hence, there is a significant relationship between user education and the security of library resources in Bayelsa State universities.

Table 2: Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Analysis of the significant relationship between the provision of security personnel at the entrance of the library and the security of the library's resources in Bayelsa State universities.

		Correlations		Decision
		Security Personnel	Security	
Security Personnel	Pearson Correlation	1	.75	Rejected
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001	
	N	78	78	
Security	Pearson Correlation	.75	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001		
	N	78	78	

*S= Significant $p < 0.05$. Legends in Table 1 applied

In the statistical analysis of research question two, a strong positive relationship was found between the provision of security personnel at the library entrance and the security of the library's resources in Bayelsa State universities. This is indicated by a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.75$ (75.0%). Furthermore, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant relationship between the provision of security personnel at the entrance of the library and the security of the library's resources in Bayelsa State universities, was rejected, and the alternative hypothesis was upheld [$P = .001$ $p < 0.05$]. Hence, there is a significant relationship between the provision of security personnel at the library entrance and the security of the library's resources in Bayelsa State universities.

Table 3: Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Analysis of the significant relationship between signage display of library rules and regulations and security of library's resources in Bayelsa State universities.

		Correlations		Decision
		Signage Display	Security	
Signage Display	Pearson Correlation	1	.42	Rejected
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	

Security	N	78	78
	Pearson Correlation	.42	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	78	78

*S= Significant $p < 0.05$. Legends in Table 1 applied

In the statistical analysis of research question 3, a moderate positive relationship was found between the signage display of library rules and regulations and the security of library resources in Bayelsa State universities. This is indicated by a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.42$ (42.0%). Furthermore, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant relationship between signage display of library rules and regulations and the security of library resources in Bayelsa State universities, was rejected, and the alternative hypothesis was upheld [$P = .000$ $p < 0.05$]. Hence, there is a significant relationship between the signage display of library rules and regulations and the security of library resources in Bayelsa State universities.

Discussion of Findings

User Education and Security of the Library's Resources

The present study's results demonstrate a statistically significant, albeit modest, positive correlation between users' level of education and the security of library resources at institutions in Bayelsa State. The correlation coefficient $r = 0.43$ and the rejection of the null hypothesis indicate that the observed association is statistically significant and not attributable to chance. The significance of these findings lies in demonstrating a positive correlation between the level of education among library users regarding rules and appropriate use and the enhanced safety of library resources. In particular, enhanced user education on library use, including familiarity with its protocols and guidelines, reduces the likelihood of resource misappropriation, including acts such as book defacement, theft, and other forms of vandalism.

The present study aligns with previous research, though some contextual and methodological variations are evident. Ferdinand et al. (2015) investigated the level of knowledge and adherence to library regulations among undergraduate students at a Nigerian institution. Although their primary emphasis differed significantly, with greater emphasis on compliance than on security, their research likewise underscores the effectiveness of user education. The students in the study demonstrated a general level of awareness and compliance, which indirectly contributed to enhanced library resource security.

Ufuoma and Urhefe (2019) conducted research examining aberrant behaviours by library users at government-owned institutions in Delta State, Nigeria. Their findings suggested implementing appropriate orientation and disciplinary actions to regulate such behaviour. This conclusion aligns with the findings of the present research conducted in Bayelsa State. The primary emphasis was on regulating deviant conduct. However, the suggestion for user education and orientation explicitly reinforces the notion that users with higher levels of education are less likely to engage in actions that jeopardise the library's security.

Bakare et al. (2021) conducted research that placed greater emphasis on the use of electronic monitoring to detect disruptive behaviours by patrons in library settings. While the main focus of their research was on technological approaches to enhance the security of library resources, the study also emphasised the need to manage user behaviour effectively, which aligns with the study's results.

In general, while the studies under evaluation differ in their specific areas of investigation and methodological frameworks, they collectively emphasise the substantial influence of user behaviour on the security of library resources. The present research is notable for its quantitative establishment of this link within the socio-educational environment of universities in Bayelsa State. Hence, this study not only contributes to the broader conversation on the security of library resources but also offers empirically grounded insights that may be of great significance to policymakers and administrators within institutions in Bayelsa State.

Provision of Security Personnel at the Entrance of the Library and Security of the Library's Resources

The research findings revealed a strong, significant correlation between the presence of security officers stationed at library entrances and the overall security of library resources at institutions in Bayelsa State. The correlation coefficient of $r = 0.75$ is particularly noteworthy, as it indicates a substantial relationship between the variables under consideration. Furthermore, the null hypothesis, which proposed the absence of a significant correlation between the two variables, was decisively refuted, thereby emphasising the need to implement human security measures to safeguard library resources.

The ramifications of this discovery are significant. The presence of security professionals at library doors strongly indicates their important role in safeguarding the security of library resources as a whole. The human presence can deter potential theft, vandalism, or other forms of abuse of library resources. This, in turn, enhances the effectiveness of technological security measures.

In the academic literature, this discovery aligns with prior research but surpasses it in several respects. In a recent scholarly investigation, Ufuoma and Urhefe (2019) examined strategies for managing deviant behaviour in library settings. Among the approaches explored, the researchers highlighted the use of security staff as a potential means of control. The researchers found that the presence of security personnel had a substantial impact on reducing instances of deviant behaviour, thereby providing further support for the conclusions of the present study. Nevertheless, the present investigation offers a more comprehensive examination by providing a quantitative assessment of the influence of security staff on the overall security of library resources at institutions in Bayelsa State.

In a recent study by Bakare, Akanbi, and Orejoko (2021), electronic monitoring tactics were primarily advocated, while acknowledging the additional benefits of human surveillance. Although not directly analogous, their recognition of the importance of human presence in security indirectly corroborates the conclusions of this study.

In contrast, Adomi's 2017 research focused primarily on electronic security measures while acknowledging the need for multiple layers of security to effectively protect library resources. The inclusion of human workers in this multi-layered strategy may suggest an indirect correlation with the findings of the present investigation.

In brief, the results of this research contribute to the current scholarly discourse by providing statistical evidence supporting a correlation between the presence of security employees and the security of library resources. Previous research has acknowledged the significance of security measures, but this study aims to provide a quantitative analysis of the effectiveness of human security at institutions in Bayelsa State. By doing so, this study contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of the safeguarding of library resources.

Signage Display of Library Rules and Regulations and Security of the Library's Resources

The results of this study show a modest yet statistically significant positive link between displaying library rules and the protection of library resources at universities in Bayelsa State. The correlation coefficient, $r = 0.42$, confirms this relationship. Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected, demonstrating a significant association between the two factors.

The findings highlight the importance of signage, which is often underestimated in library security, overshadowed by electronic security measures or staff. The study shows that clear, visible guidelines significantly help protect the integrity and safety of library resources. Such signs serve as continuous reminders to users about the rules governing their behaviour, encouraging compliance and reducing misuse.

In the context of prior academic research, this study's findings provide valuable insights into the growing body of literature. For example, Ferdinand, Nneka, and Eghworo's 2015 study on user compliance with library rules indirectly supports these results. Their research found a high level of user awareness and adherence to library regulations, suggesting that signs can effectively promote security.

This focus on awareness aligns with existing studies that assess how consciousness contributes to better resource security.

Ufuoma and Urhefe (2019) emphasised the importance of direction and discipline in managing disruptive behaviour among library users. While signage was not their main focus, their findings suggest that any method, like signage to convey rules, that helps establish discipline and guidance among users, is expected to yield beneficial outcomes.

The current research enhances our understanding by introducing a novel perspective on perceptions of library security measures, particularly within institutions in Bayelsa State. The correlation between signs pertaining to rules and regulations and the security of library resources is both modest and noteworthy. This underscores the need to adopt a comprehensive strategy for library security that integrates human, electronic, and informational components in a unified manner.

Conclusion

This research aimed to comprehensively examine the factors influencing the security of library resources in institutions in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The study sought to analyse the relationships between several key variables, including user education, the presence of security personnel, and the display of signage outlining library rules and regulations, to understand how these elements contribute to safeguarding library resources. To facilitate this exploration, the study formulated specific research questions and hypotheses designed to examine these relationships in detail. Employing rigorous statistical methods, the research tested the validity of each hypothesis, thereby deepening understanding of the complex interconnections and dynamics that underpin library resource security in this context.

Recommendations

Based on the study's findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance the security of university library resources in Bayelsa State:

1. **Strengthen User Education Programmes:** Given the strong link between user education and protecting library resources, institutions should consider investing more in user education initiatives. Offering workshops, seminars, and orientation sessions focused on library rules and ethical use of resources can significantly reduce misconduct such as mutilation, other damaging behaviours, and theft.
2. **Increase Security Personnel at Entrance Points:** To improve resource security, colleges should increase the number of trained security personnel stationed at library entrances and other key areas. There is a strong positive association between the presence of security staff and resource protection. These staff members can perform thorough inspections, helping to prevent unauthorised removal of library items.
3. **Prominently Display Library Rules and Regulations:** This study found a significant link between clear display of library rules and resource security. Therefore, libraries should improve rule visibility by using plain language and infographics, ensuring that all users clearly understand the expected behaviour.

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